

AUTOMATION OF PARTICLE COUNTING AND SIZE CHARACTERISATION IN MICROSCOPY IMAGES

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

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Executive summary

A script was developed to count particles and characterise their size distribution in image datasets obtained by optical or electron microscopy. The use of the script removes the need for manual analysis of images and allows for automated and high-throughput analysis of samples. This work was undertaken under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication” of the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project.

1 Description of the work

Recently, the Micro/Nano Particle Characterisation Facility within the Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis (CMM) at The University of Queensland, opened its doors to clients. The aim of the Facility is to provide clients with access to a range of different particle characterisation instrumentation to enable full characterisation of their particulate samples in a reliable and representative manner.

Typically, techniques such as dynamic light scattering and laser diffraction are available and allow for analysis of large particle numbers, but these techniques rely on the assumption that the particles are spherical, which is not always the case. It is therefore important to enable a complementary technique such as optical or electron microscopy to be used for analysis of these larger numbers of particles. A limitation of particle size and shape analysis by microscopy is the relatively small number of particles that data can be obtained from. By using array (or mapping) microscopy a larger sampling area can be imaged resulting in particle numbers in the thousands, thereby giving a representative population of the entire sample.

When considering the size and shape analysis of such large numbers of particles, an automated image analysis is required. This enables accurate and reliable analysis of each of these particles in a batch of images. This was the motivation to develop an automated particle-counting script. In addition to the benefit of high throughput, the script also removes the need for time-consuming manual image-by-image analysis and removes the effect of human error from the measurements.

The developed script can process a batch of images automatically, using FIJI and python to provide size and shape information on large particle numbers. In brief, the script removes any unsuitable images from the batch based on percentage of pixels over a chosen intensity, thresholds the images, performs the particle analysis function available in FIJI, records the values for chosen size and shape parameters in a `csv` file and saves an image showing the particle outlines with numbers that can be referred back to in the `csv` file. Figure 1 shows an example of image processing by the script. The script then compiles the `csv` files into one final

Figure 1 Example of a dataset (1 μm silica particles) processed using the particle-counting script. Images were acquired using the Olympus DSX1000 optical microscope at CMM. *Left to right*, original image, thresholded image produced by the script, and particle outlines and count produced by the script.

file containing all the particles from all the images, plots a frequency distribution of the Feret diameter and generates a table of summary data (mean, standard deviation, percentiles) (Figure 2). The script has been tested on several data sets from different instruments. It is now available publicly on GitHub¹ for client use, although validation of the results continues.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.5: “Identify opportunities to accelerate research by automating repetitive tasks. Prototype an easy-to-use solution to cater batch jobs or pipelines for repetitive tasks”.

Figure 2 Frequency distribution plot of the Feret diameter of particles and summary data generated using the particle-counting script. The dataset used in input is the same dataset used in Figure 1.

2 Contributorship

HN designed the work and developed the script. AW tested the script and wrote the final report.

¹ <https://github.com/microcmm/ParticleCounting>